

Uranium (VI)-8-Hydroxy Quinoline-7-Sulfonic Acid Chelate : A Spectrophotometric Study

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The formation of orange red chelate between hexavalent uranium and 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid has been studied in aqueous medium spectrophotometrically. The chelate is stable in the pH range 5 to 6.5. The composition of the chelate has been determined by three different methods and found that a stable complex is formed between one mole of uranium(VI) and two moles of the reagent. The stability constant in aqueous medium determined by the method of Banerji and Dey and by the mole-ratio method was found to be $\log K = 8.9 \pm 0.06$ and the free energy of formation -12.29 k.cal/mole at 25° . The effect of ionic strength and temperature on the chelate has been investigated. The enthalpy change and entropy change are -3 k.cal/mole and 59 e.u. respectively. The interference of various ions in the measurement of colour and the probable structure of the chelate in the solution are also suggested.

The ability of 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid to form metal chelates is due to the periposition of the phenolic hydroxyl group to the hetero atom nitrogen, forming a grouping N-C-C-O which can give rise to a formation of five-membered ring with the metal ion. In recent communications from this laboratory Banerji and co-workers¹ reported the preparation of 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid and its colour reactions with various metal ions and the physico-chemical investigation of its iron chelate regarding the composition, structure and stability². The present communication deals with the study of the formation of the orange red chelate between the hexavalent uranium and 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid in aqueous medium by using spectrophotometric methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solution of uranium was prepared by dissolving uranyl nitrate (A.R.) in double distilled water. A purified sample of the sodium salt of 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid was used for the preparation of stock solution in aqueous medium. Suitable standard solutions were prepared from this solution by dilution. Hydrogen ion concentrations were adjusted with sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. Extremely dilute solutions were used so that the contraction in volume, if any, would be negligible. Stock solutions of diverse ions were prepared from the nitrate or chloride of the corresponding metal. All other reagents were of analytical grade and were used without further purification.

All the absorption measurements were made on a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer (Model H 700-308) equipped with thermoplates to stabilise the temperature of the cell holder. The matched glass cells were of 10 mm thickness, as supplied by the manufacturers.

1. K. C. Srivastava and S. K. Banerji, *Chem. Age of India*, 1967, **18**, 351.
2. K. Balachandran and S. K. Banerji, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1968, **37**, 263.

Concentrations were chosen so that the absorbance readings changed from 0.2 to 0.7. All readings checked within 0.2% in absorbance. The hydrogen ion concentration of all the solutions was measured with a Beckman pH-meter (Model H2). All the experiments were performed at 25°.

RESULTS

Absorbance curve : To an aliquot quantity of uranium solution ($4 \times 10^{-4} M$), taken in a 25 ml flask, the reagent solution was added ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) and the volume was finally made to 25 ml after adjusting the pH 5.8. A reagent solution was also prepared under similar conditions. The absorbance of the orange red coloured chelate were then measured against water blank at different wavelengths. Fig. 1 shows the absorbance of the reagent and the coloured solution decreases gradually as wavelength increases; but from 470 $m\mu$ to higher wavelength, the absorbance of the reagent is very small. Therefore all the colour measurements were made at 470 $m\mu$.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Uranium(VI)-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid chelate (curve 1) and reagent alone (curve 2) against water blank.

Effect of pH on the complex : Solutions containing uranyl nitrate and the reagent were prepared at different hydrogen ion concentrations and the absorbance at various wavelengths were taken. The complex was found to be stable in the pH range 5 to 6.5. For subsequent studies pH 5.8 was selected since the complex developed maximum colour intensity in this pH.

Effect of time and temperature on the colour of the chelate : Colour formation was observed to be instantaneous and it was found that even up to 48 hr there was no change in absorbance values at room temperature. Order of reagent addition was not a significant variable. Temperature change had little effect on the colour formation when the ligand is present in excess. When the ligand is not in excess the intensity of the colour increases with increase in temperature because of the accelerated interaction between the metal ion and the complexing reagent. It was decided to perform subsequent experiments at room temperature (25°), so that a constant condition may be maintained.

Fig. 2. Job's method,
 Curve 1, $c = 12 \times 10^{-4} M$
 Curve 2, $c = 8 \times 10^{-4} M$
 Curve 3, $c = 6 \times 10^{-4} M$

Nature of the complex in solution : The empirical formula of Uranium (VI)-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid chelate was established by three independent methods : the continuous variation method of Job³ as modified by Vosburg and Cooper⁴; the slope-ratio method

3. P. Job, *Annals Chem.*, 1928, 9, (10) 113.

4. Vosburg and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1630.

of Harvey and Manning⁵ and the mole-ratio method of Yoe and Jones⁶, (Figs. 2 and 3). The results indicate the formation of the complex between one mole of UO_2^{+2} and two moles of the reagent. Consequently the following tentative structure is postulated.

Evaluation of stability constant: For the purpose of the determination of stability constant of the complex, calculations have been made from the optical density data by the method of Banerji and Dey⁷ and the mole-ratio of Yoe and Jones⁶. In this system the ratio of the reactants is 1 : 2.

$$\text{The formation constant } K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where 'x' is the concentration of the complex at equilibrium and 'a' and 'b' are the initial concentrations of metal ion and the chelating agent, respectively. Taking two concentrations with the same optical density, i.e., the same value of 'x' we have

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a'-x)(b'-2x)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

Thus from the knowledge of the initial concentrations of 'a' and 'b' the value of 'x' can be calculated from eqn. 2. By substituting the value of 'x' in eqn. 1, K can be found out.

Fig. 3. Mole-ratio method, final concentration of the metal in curve 1 = $4 \times 10^{-4}M$, curve 2 = $2 \times 10^{-4}M$.

The stability constant has been calculated from mole-ratio curve also, through the calculation of degree of dissociation. The stability constant K is given by the equation

$$K = \frac{(1-\alpha)}{4\alpha^3c^2}$$

5. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
6. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Edn.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
7. S. K. Banerji and A. K. Dey, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **30**, 179.

where 'c' is the concentration of the complex and α is the degree of dissociation. The degree of dissociation is given by the equation

$$\alpha = (Em - Es)/Em$$

where Em is the absorbance of the complex when excess of the reagent is present and Es is the absorbance of the complex at equivalent point.

The values obtained by these methods have been found to be in close agreement and $\log K$ in the system Uranium (VI)-8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonic acid chelate works out to be 8.9 ± 0.6 at 25° .

The free energy of formation ΔF° has also been calculated according to Vant Hoff isotherm

$$\Delta F^\circ = RT \ln K$$

where R is the gas constant; T the absolute temperature and K the formation constant.

Effect of diverse ions : In the optical density measurements of the orange red uranium 8-hydroxy quinoline-7-sulfonate in solution, foreign ions like oxalate, iron, cerium, thorium, titanium, vanadium, zirconium and molybdenum are found to interfere even when present in minute quantities. Large quantities of acetate, phosphate, borate, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, nickel, lead, cobalt, manganese, lanthanum and beryllium had no effect.

Entropy and enthalpy changes : In view of the difficulty of obtaining the thermodynamic stability constant, we have determined the entropy and enthalpy changes at pH 5.8 and ionic strength 0.02. The stability constant and free energy of formation of the complex at various temperatures are shown in Table I. From the slope of the curve obtained by plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$, ΔH of the reaction has been calculated and found to be -5.3 k.cal/mole. Assuming this to be constant over a range of experimental temperatures ΔS of the reaction has been calculated and found to be 59 e.u.

TABLE I

Log K at various temperatures (at ionic strength 0.02 and pH 5.8)

T	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
$\log K$	8.90	8.96	9.04	9.06	9.14
ΔF°	-12.39	-12.46	-12.83	-13.05	-13.35

Table II records the stability constants of the complex at various ionic strengths (at pH 5.8 and temp. 25°). The results indicate that the stability constant decreases with an increase in ionic strength as expected, but beyond ionic strength 0.3 the value of K remains almost constant. This is probably due to the fact that the activity coefficient of an ion passes through the minimum as the ionic strength increases.

TABLE II

Variation of stability constant with ionic strength (pH 5.8)

Ionic strength	0.02	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
$K \times 10^{-8}$	8.02	7.53	6.85	6.25	6.05	5.96	5.96

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